

SURVEY ON SEX MATTERS, HUMAN REPRODUCTION, SEXUALLY TRANSMITTED DISEASES (STDs), AND CONTRACEPTION

INFORMED CONSENT

You are kindly requested to participate in a survey study. In this survey you will fill in a questionnaire concerning awareness on Sex Matters and Human Reproduction, Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) including HIV infection, AIDS and Contraception. The procedure is not expected to last more than ten minutes. The results of this anonymous survey could be used and discussed during the exhibit on "Human Reproduction, Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) and Contraception" in the Biology Lab as part of the course Introduction to Biology I lab activity and possibly be scientifically communicated.

There are no right or wrong answers. The survey is completely anonymous.

By clicking START SURVEY you are verifying that you have read the explanation of the study, and that you agree to participate. You also understand that your participation in this study is strictly voluntary.

* Required

1. *

Mark only one oval.

Start Survey

Survey Questions

2. 1. What is your gender? *

Mark only one oval.

Female

Male

3. 2. What is your age? *

Mark only one oval.

18-24

25-30

31-40

41 and above

4. 3. Number of years at Deree:

Mark only one oval.

4

3

2

1 or less

5. 4. Field of Study:

6. 5. Other University degree/Parallel studies:

7. 6. Parents' Education:

Mark only one oval per row.

	Up to High school	University degree	Postgraduate studies	PhD
Mother	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Father	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

8. 7. Have you participated in any of the following? If yes, when? *

Check all that apply.

	Yes	No	Partly/ Superficially	If yes, when: Recently	If yes when: One year back	If yes when: 2 years or more
Sex education training in high school	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Biology I course at Deree	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Biology II course at Deree	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other university courses where you were exposed to sex education, human reproduction, STDs and contraception	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

9. 8. Please check the appropriate answer for each of the following statements. *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I am well informed in the matters of sex	<input type="radio"/>				
My partner is well informed about sex. (if not applicable, please skip the question)	<input type="radio"/>				
I am well informed about contraceptive methods.	<input type="radio"/>				
I know how Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) are transmitted.	<input type="radio"/>				
I understand the difference among the various microorganisms causing STDs	<input type="radio"/>				
I know about the different types of treatment of STDs	<input type="radio"/>				
I know how to practice safe sex	<input type="radio"/>				

All STDs are curable

10. 9. Do you prefer: *

Mark only one oval.

Stable relationships

Changing partners from time to time

Having a lot of relationships

One-night stand relationships

Abstinence

Other: _____

11. 10. Are you sexually actively involved with: *

Mark only one oval.

One person

Two or more

None

12. 11. How long have you been sexually active: *

Mark only one oval.

- Not active
- Up to 1 year
- 1-5 years
- More than 5 years

13. 12. How would you characterize yourself: *

Mark only one oval.

- Heterosexual
- Bisexual
- Homosexual
- Other: _____

14. 13. Have you ever had a Sexually Transmitted Disease (STD)? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Not sure
- Don't know

15. 14. If you have never had a Sexually Transmitted Disease (STD), how do you know? *

Mark only one oval.

- Because I've never had any symptoms
- Because I've been tested
- Because I've never had sexual intercourse
- This question doesn't apply because I have had an STD
- Other: _____

16. 15. Please check the appropriate answer for each of the following statements. If you have experienced or are thinking of having sex, ... *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
...You use/will use a condom each time	<input type="radio"/>				
...You only have/will only have sex with your sexual partner	<input type="radio"/>				
...You avoid anal sex	<input type="radio"/>				
...You avoid oral sex	<input type="radio"/>				
...You avoid oral sex when you have a mouth ulcer or wound on your genitals.	<input type="radio"/>				
...You can have it during menstruation	<input type="radio"/>				
...You will use two condoms at the same time	<input type="radio"/>				
...You will request that your sexual partner will take a blood test beforehand	<input type="radio"/>				
...You will take a blood	<input type="radio"/>				

**test yourself in
advance**

**...You do not have sex
without contraception**

17. 16. Do you use some form of contraception?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

18. 16a. If yes, what kind of contraceptive method(s) do you use?

19. 17. If you are a female, have you visited a gynecologist?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

20. 17a. If yes: When was the first time?

21. 17b. If yes: When was the last time?

22. 17c. If yes: How often do you visit your gynecologist?

23. 18. Please check the appropriate answer for each of the following statements... *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I believe a condom helps prevent sexually transmitted diseases	<input type="radio"/>				
Anal sex poses a higher risk of HIV infection than vaginal sex	<input type="radio"/>				
I believe that people should be tested for STDs including HIV as part of annual checkups	<input type="radio"/>				
I talk about sexual issues with my parents, siblings and friends because that helps minimize misconceptions about sexual issues and give correct preventive guidelines	<input type="radio"/>				
I believe you gain greater satisfaction from sex if it is done without a condom	<input type="radio"/>				
The price of a condom	<input type="radio"/>				

**The price of a condom
is an important factor
influencing my
decision to use a
condom**

**If I am sexually
aroused, I choose to
perform masturbation
because I believe that
it is an effective way
to prevent sexually
transmitted diseases**

**I believe STD cases in
Greece are high**

**I believe abortion
rates in Greece are
high**

24. 19. How risky for contracting a Sexually Transmitted Disease (STD) do you think it is if one practices ... (Please check the appropriate answer for each statement below.) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very risky	Somewhat risky	A little risky	Not at all risky
Sexual intercourse without protection?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Oral sex?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Anal sex?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sexual intercourse with a single partner?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sexual intercourse with several partners?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sexual intercourse with people you meet once?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

25. 20. What do you fear the most considering sex? *

26. 21. Normally, how long does an egg survive after ovulation in the female body? *

27. 22. Normally, how long does sperm survive in the female body?

28. 23. Normally, when does ovulation of an egg occur in a 30-day cycle?

29. 24. Which contraceptive methods do you know of? Name a few. *

30. 25. Which form of contraception has the least potential health side effects?

31. 26. Which sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) are you familiar with? Name a few.

32. 27. What is the most important source(s) of information about sex matters? *

Mark only one oval.

- Partners
- Friends
- Doctors
- School education
- Books
- Internet
- Social media
- Other: _____

33. 28. Do you find the Deree Biology courses as a good source of information on sex matters? *

Mark only one oval.

- As an introduction
- As complimentary information to what you already know
- Not a significant source of information
- I have not yet considered sex issues in any Deree course

34. 29. In my view, the most effective way(s) to promote knowledge about sex, contraception and STDs is/are:

35. 30. In my view, the most effective way(s) to promote safe sexual behaviors is/are:

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